

Enhancing IoT Security: A Study of Secure Authentication and Onboarding Mechanisms in Connected Devices

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Abstract

The proliferation of connected devices and the widespread adoption of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies have introduced a paradigm shift in how networks, systems, and physical infrastructures operate. From smart homes and industrial automation to critical infrastructures such as energy and healthcare, IoT devices now form the backbone of cyber-physical systems. However, their explosive growth has brought significant challenges in terms of lifecycle security, particularly during the onboarding and post-deployment phases. These stages are critical: onboarding is the point at which trust must be established, while lifecycle security ensures that devices behave according to defined policies and remain protected against evolving threats.

In traditional IoT deployments, onboarding typically requires manual procedures such as scanning QR codes, entering pre-shared keys, or configuring access credentials manually through web interfaces or vendor-specific platforms. These approaches are inherently insecure and unscalable. They introduce operational friction and are highly prone to misconfiguration, especially in environments where large numbers of devices must be deployed quickly. Moreover, these methods lack interoperability and often lead to vendor lock-in, limiting the flexibility and long-term sustainability of IoT solutions.

Beyond the initial deployment, the absence of standardized post-onboarding policy enforcement mechanisms has proven to be a significant weakness. Devices are frequently deployed with default or loosely configured access rules, leaving them vulnerable to abuse, misrouting, or unintended lateral movement within networks. Existing access control solutions are either too generic—failing to consider the specific behavior profile of each device—or too complex to deploy at scale, especially in constrained environments with limited computational or administrative resources.

To address these challenges, this work presents an integrated and standards-based security framework for connected devices, combining secure onboarding, automatic policy enforcement, and dynamic threat mitigation. The architecture is composed of three core components:

- **FIDO Device Onboard (FDO) [1]**: A protocol developed by the FIDO Alliance to enable secure, zero-touch onboarding of devices. FDO uses asymmetric cryptography, vouchers, and a rendezvous-based architecture to securely transfer device ownership at deployment time without requiring prior trust relationships or manual configuration.
- **Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) [2][3]**: A framework standardized by the IETF in RFC 8520, which allows device manufacturers to publish a formal description of the intended network behavior of their devices. MUD policies are expressed in a structured format and can be retrieved and enforced automatically by network managers, enabling fine-grained access control tailored to each device type.

- **Threat MUD [2]:** An extension proposed and implemented in this work that enables dynamic security policy updates in response to new vulnerabilities or threats. Threat MUD files describe additional restrictions or changes that must be applied to devices affected by a specific threat, and are distributed through Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) integration.

This architecture creates a unified lifecycle security model that begins with secure onboarding (FDO), transitions into policy enforcement (MUD), and evolves into threat-responsive behavior (Threat MUD). By integrating these components, devices are not only onboarded securely but also governed automatically according to predefined policies, and protected dynamically as new security challenges arise.

To validate the proposal, a complete prototype was implemented using open-source tools and technologies. The onboarding workflow was developed using the official `pri-fidoiot` implementation maintained by the FIDO Alliance. The MUD and Threat MUD components were developed in Python, using REST interfaces to emulate real-world interactions with policy managers and network enforcers. A containerized testbed was created using Docker, replicating all the roles in the architecture: device emulator, manufacturer, rendezvous server, owner server, MUD file server, policy manager, and enforcement layer. This modular design enabled precise measurements and repeatable experiments.

Multiple metrics were evaluated to assess the integration, automation, and responsiveness of the proposed lifecycle security framework. The aim was not to evaluate enforcement scalability or rule processing complexity, but rather to validate the correctness and efficiency of integrating FDO, MUD, and Threat MUD into a cohesive and automated workflow:

- **Onboarding time:** This metric captures the duration from the start of the FDO process (TO1) until the ownership is transferred and the MUD URL is extracted and forwarded to the MUD Manager. Results consistently showed that onboarding was completed in under 600 milliseconds. This confirms that extending the FDO flow to include metadata exchange with MUD infrastructure introduces negligible overhead, making it suitable even for constrained environments or large-scale provisioning scenarios.
- **Policy retrieval and coordination latency:** Once the MUD URL is forwarded, the system retrieves the MUD file, validates its digital signature, and triggers automated translation and dispatch to the orchestrator. While the enforcement phase involves applying basic rule sets (only two rules per MUD in this work), the pipeline itself—particularly the automated handoff between services—was validated to complete in approximately 374 milliseconds. This highlights the seamless orchestration and integration rather than the performance of bulk policy application.
- **Threat response time:** The Threat MUD mechanism demonstrated that upon reception of a threat alert (in the form of a Threat ID), the system could retrieve, validate, and propagate updated mitigation rules to the enforcement layer in less than 100 milliseconds. While the rule complexity remained minimal, the emphasis here is on validating the reactive capability of the architecture and its ability to incorporate dynamic security updates without human intervention.

These results confirm that the full lifecycle—from onboarding to behavior definition and dynamic threat reaction—can be orchestrated in an automated and timely manner. The

architecture proves its viability as a standards-based, regulation-ready framework capable of securing IoT devices from deployment through operational life, with integration as the primary enabler.

Additionally, the implementation was benchmarked against alternative solutions including manual provisioning, TPM-based onboarding, Wi-Fi EasyConnect (DPP)[4], and proprietary cloud-based IoT platforms. These comparisons revealed that the proposed architecture not only achieves comparable or superior security guarantees but also exceeds in terms of automation, standards compliance, and lifecycle coverage.

Beyond performance, the design philosophy emphasizes interoperability and future extensibility. All components are loosely coupled, communicate over open protocols, and rely on established standards such as RFC 8520 (MUD)[3] and the FDO protocol specification[1]. This ensures compatibility with existing network infrastructure and opens the door to further integration with Software-Defined Networking (SDN), threat feeds such as MISP, and compliance automation platforms.

In the context of upcoming regulatory requirements, particularly the European Union’s Cyber Resilience Act (CRA)[5], this work provides a concrete foundation for secure-by-design and secure-by-default principles. By making onboarding cryptographically verifiable, enforcing behavior constraints based on manufacturer intent, and enabling proactive response to emerging threats, the architecture supports traceable and auditable device security from the point of manufacture to runtime operation.

The proposed model also highlights an architectural shift in how IoT security should be approached: rather than relying solely on reactive measures (e.g., patching, firmware updates), the emphasis is placed on proactive control, formal behavior descriptions, and dynamic adaptation at the network level. This paradigm is not only more scalable but also more suitable for constrained environments where device software cannot always be updated or trusted.

To conclude, this thesis contributes a functional, reproducible, and standards-based framework for secure onboarding and lifecycle security in connected devices. It combines cutting-edge technologies, aligns with regulatory expectations, and demonstrates significant improvements in automation, performance, and resilience compared to traditional methods. The results and lessons learned from this work provide a strong foundation for future research in IoT security orchestration, as well as for practical implementations in industry, smart environments, and critical infrastructure protection.

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1 Introduction

The exponential growth of connected devices and the proliferation of the Internet of Things (IoT) are transforming industries, homes, and critical infrastructures. These devices are increasingly deployed in environments with limited physical or administrative control, making them attractive targets for cyber threats. Despite advances in hardware and cloud platforms, fundamental aspects of device onboarding, configuration, and lifecycle security remain weakly standardized, often relying on manual processes, vendor-specific logic, or static credentials.

In this context, it is important to distinguish between two closely related concepts:

Onboarding refers to the initial process through which a device is securely introduced into an IoT environment. This involves establishing trust, exchanging credentials, and ensuring that the device can communicate securely with its intended owner or management infrastructure. Traditionally, onboarding required manual configuration, including the provisioning of pre-shared keys or certificates, which often resulted in weak security guarantees and poor scalability.

Bootstrapping, on the other hand, can be seen as a broader and more continuous process. While onboarding is usually a one-time action, bootstrapping encompasses not only the initial authentication but also the automated configuration and secure policy enforcement that follow. It ensures that once the device is authenticated, it is also correctly integrated into the network's access control and management architecture. In this sense, secure bootstrapping covers both the establishment of trust and the application of constraints and policies that define what a device is allowed to do.

This situation introduces considerable challenges for operators, manufacturers, and regulators. From a security perspective, improper onboarding can lead to unauthorized access, rogue devices, and lateral movement within networks. From an operational standpoint, the lack of automation increases deployment time and cost. Furthermore, most IoT devices are constrained in computational and memory resources, making it difficult to embed traditional endpoint protection mechanisms. Therefore, security must be introduced at the network and architectural level from the moment a device is first introduced into a system. This work is particularly relevant in the context of increasing regulatory demands for IoT security, including the European Union's Cyber Resilience Act (CRA), which mandates secure development, deployment, and maintenance of connected products.

To address these issues, this work explores the integration of three complementary technologies:

- **FIDO Device Onboard (FDO)[6][1]**: A secure and standardized protocol for zero-touch onboarding of IoT devices, enabling ownership transfer with minimal configuration or prior trust between device and operator.
- **Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD)[3]**: A network-layer policy framework allowing manufacturers to define and publish the intended communication behavior of

their devices, enabling automated access control enforcement after onboarding.

- **Threat MUD[2]:** An extension to the MUD framework that allows dynamic updates to access policies in response to detected vulnerabilities or threats, closing the loop between cyber threat intelligence and network-level mitigation.

This work is motivated by the need to address three critical security gaps that persist in IoT deployments: the absence of a standardized, secure, and automated onboarding mechanism; the lack of device-specific policy enforcement immediately after deployment; and the inability to dynamically mitigate vulnerabilities as they are discovered during the device’s operational lifetime. The proposed solution addresses these challenges by combining secure onboarding through FDO, access control enforcement based on manufacturer-declared behavior via MUD, and dynamic, threat-driven mitigation using Threat MUD. This integrated architecture enables device security that is not only automated and scalable, but also adaptive and resilient—essential attributes in increasingly interconnected and risk-prone IoT environments.

By adopting standard protocols and focusing on automation and lifecycle resilience, this thesis aims to contribute a practical and scalable solution to one of the most pressing security challenges in modern connected environments.

The primary goal of this work is to design, implement, and evaluate a modular architecture that enables secure onboarding and lifecycle-aware security for IoT devices, integrating FDO, MUD, and Threat MUD mechanisms.

This main objective addresses the need for automation, scalability, and dynamic policy adaptation in the context of increasingly connected environments, where manual provisioning and static configurations are no longer sufficient.

To achieve this, the following specific objectives have been defined:

1. **Analyze the limitations of traditional onboarding and policy enforcement mechanisms** in IoT environments, and identify key gaps in automation, standardization, and threat response.
 2. **Integrate the FDO protocol** into a testbed to demonstrate secure and zero-touch onboarding, including the delivery of metadata such as MUD URLs.
 3. **Implement an automatic policy enforcement system using MUD**, capable of retrieving, validating, and translating MUD files into enforceable access control rules at the network layer.
 4. **Extend the MUD framework with Threat MUD capabilities**, allowing for the dynamic update of policies in response to emerging vulnerabilities through a simulated cyber threat intelligence (CTI) channel.
 5. **Develop a functional and reproducible test environment**, using containerized components that simulate all relevant roles (manufacturer, rendezvous, owner, enforcer).
 6. **Evaluate the performance and responsiveness of the architecture**, measuring onboarding latency, rule translation overhead, threat mitigation time, and comparing these to traditional approaches.
-

7. **Demonstrate the feasibility of the architecture under real-world conditions**, emphasizing automation, standards compliance, and alignment with current regulatory initiatives such as the EU Cyber Resilience Act (CRA).

These objectives guide the development and validation of a cohesive, standards-based approach to secure onboarding and lifecycle protection for IoT, with a focus on automation, policy accuracy, and adaptive threat mitigation.

This work has been developed within the scope of the European research project **DOSS (Secure-by-Design IoT Operation with Supply Chain Control)**, which aims to enhance the security and trustworthiness of IoT ecosystems by integrating secure-by-design principles across the entire device lifecycle—from manufacturing to operation and decommissioning. The contribution of this thesis directly aligns with the objectives of DOSS by addressing secure onboarding through FDO, behavior-based access control via MUD, and dynamic threat mitigation using Threat MUD. The integration and evaluation of these mechanisms in a unified architecture demonstrate a practical approach to automating device provisioning and policy enforcement. Moreover, the work serves as a foundational implementation to support future demonstrations and validations within DOSS, particularly in environments where supply chain integrity and lifecycle policy automation are critical.

This memory is separated into abstract, resume, and the next six chapters:

This document is structured in six chapters. Chapter 1 introduces the context of the Internet of Things security landscape, highlighting the motivation and objectives of this work. Chapter 2 reviews the state of the art, exploring existing solutions for secure onboarding, access control, and dynamic threat mitigation, with a focus on standards such as FDO, MUD, and recent proposals related to Threat MUD. Chapter 3 presents the analysis of the problem and the specific goals to be achieved, along with the methodology used to design and validate the proposed architecture. Chapter 4 describes the system design and implementation in detail, including the integration of open-source components, the communication flow between modules, and the testbed configuration. Chapter 5 reports the experimental results, providing quantitative evaluations of onboarding latency, policy enforcement time, and mitigation effectiveness, as well as comparisons with traditional approaches. Finally, Chapter 6 concludes the work, summarizing the key contributions and outlining future lines of research and possible improvements to the proposed framework.

2 State of art

As the number of connected devices continues to grow, establishing secure, scalable, and automated initialization processes has become a cornerstone of IoT security. Two key concepts emerge in this context: *onboarding* and *bootstrapping*. Although they are closely related, each addresses a different phase in the secure integration of devices into a networked ecosystem.

This section reviews the state of the art in secure onboarding and lifecycle security for IoT systems, focusing on the technical challenges and emerging standards that address different stages of the device lifecycle. Securely integrating IoT devices into network environments involves complex issues across both the onboarding and post-deployment phases, compounded by heterogeneous device capabilities, constrained resources, the absence of unified standards, and evolving cyber threats. Before detailing concrete solutions, it is essential to understand the risks and limitations that compromise security at these stages. Two particularly promising approaches are examined: the *FDO* protocol, which automates and secures the onboarding process through cryptographic ownership transfer, and the *MUD* framework, which supports post-onboarding access control and adaptive policy enforcement. Together, these technologies form a foundation for scalable, standards-based, and threat-aware IoT security.

2.1 Security Challenges in IoT Onboarding

The onboarding and lifecycle management of IoT devices present multiple security challenges that impact device integrity, data privacy, and network security. Recent research highlights several critical security concerns that must be addressed to ensure the robustness of IoT ecosystems [7, 8, 9].

- **Lack of standardized onboarding protocols.** The diversity of IoT device manufacturers and the absence of widely accepted onboarding standards result in fragmented security practices. Traditional onboarding approaches often rely on pre-shared keys or manual configurations, making them vulnerable to attacks [7]. Some frameworks, such as the Eclipse Arrowhead project, introduce automated and secure onboarding mechanisms for System of Systems (SoS) environments to mitigate these risks [7].
- **Weak authentication mechanisms.** Many IoT devices employ inadequate authentication techniques, such as default credentials or weak cryptographic methods, which can be easily exploited. The FDO protocol attempts to address this by introducing Ownership Vouchers and cryptographic attestation, but concerns remain regarding its reliance on potentially weak elliptic curves (SECP256r1/SECP384r1) and centralized trust models [8].
- **Supply chain vulnerabilities.** A major challenge in IoT onboarding is the risk of compromise at different points in the supply chain. Trust delegation from manufacturers

to distributors and retailers introduces multiple attack vectors, including malicious tampering or key exposure. The ASOP protocol proposes an alternative that applies zero-trust principles and post-quantum cryptography (CRYSTALS-Kyber) to mitigate these risks [8].

- **Insecure communication channels.** Many IoT devices operate over insecure or poorly configured communication protocols, exposing them to man-in-the-middle attacks and eavesdropping. Research highlights the importance of mutual authentication and encryption during onboarding, particularly in industrial environments where compromised communication can have severe operational consequences [7].
- **Scalability issues in secure device management.** As IoT networks expand, managing security at scale becomes increasingly complex. The heterogeneity of devices, each with unique security requirements, makes centralized management difficult. Studies suggest that a service-oriented architecture (SoA)-based approach, such as the Eclipse Arrowhead framework, can improve scalability and interoperability while maintaining strong security postures [7].
- **Lifecycle management and secure decommissioning.** IoT security must extend beyond the onboarding phase to include secure lifecycle management and decommissioning. Improperly decommissioned devices may still retain sensitive credentials or configuration data, posing persistent security risks. Automated onboarding procedures should incorporate certificate revocation mechanisms and secure key disposal to prevent unauthorized access post-deployment [7].

Recent research in secure onboarding protocols, such as ASOP and FDO, aim to mitigate these challenges, but concerns remain regarding centralized trust, supply chain security, and cryptographic robustness [7, 8]. The integration of post-quantum cryptography and decentralized trust models presents a promising direction for future work.

Furthermore, ensuring the secure deployment of IoT devices in real-world environments requires continuous policy enforcement and dynamic response mechanisms. Secure deployment implies that once a device is authenticated and integrated into the network, its behavior remains constrained to a defined set of legitimate operations. This is especially relevant in contexts where unauthorized communication or unexpected behavior could pose significant risks to operational continuity or data confidentiality. The MUD framework emerges as a foundational tool in this space, enabling the automatic enforcement of access control policies based on manufacturer-provided specifications.

In parallel, the growing regulatory landscape in Europe—particularly with the upcoming CRA—is reinforcing the need for built-in security mechanisms across the entire device lifecycle. The CRA introduces binding obligations for manufacturers to provide secure-by-design products, enforce strict access control policies, and ensure continued vulnerability management post-deployment. These regulatory pressures underscore the importance of integrating solutions like FDO and MUD, not only from a technical perspective but also as part of compliance and risk management strategies. This broader context serves as a key motivation for the current research, which explores how the combination of secure onboarding and policy enforcement can meet both security and regulatory expectations in IoT deployments.

2.2 Overview of the FIDO Device Onboard (FDO) Protocol

The FIDO Device Onboard (FDO) protocol [6] is a security framework designed to simplify and strengthen the process of introducing IoT devices into their operational environments. FDO addresses long-standing challenges associated with secure onboarding, particularly those related to manual provisioning, pre-shared secrets, and inflexible manufacturing-to-deployment pipelines. Rather than relying on static credentials embedded during production, FDO allows device credentials and ownership to be assigned during deployment using a principle known as late binding [1].

At the core of FDO is a cryptographic mechanism based on ownership vouchers. These digitally signed tokens are issued by the manufacturer and passed down through the supply chain, enabling the final device owner to assert control securely and verifiably. The device, upon first boot, contacts a rendezvous server included in the voucher metadata. This rendezvous server serves as an intermediary, redirecting the device to the appropriate owner service without requiring pre-established configuration. Ownership is then transferred through a sequence of authenticated exchanges that include cryptographic key negotiation, attestation, and encrypted provisioning data delivery.

Figure 2.1: FDO Onboarding Process Sequence Diagram

As we can see in Figure 2.1 FDO incorporates multiple ownership transfer protocols, each serving a specific function in securely transitioning a device from manufacturer to owner:

- Device Initialize Protocol (DI) - Establishes initial device credentials during manufacturing.
- Transfer Ownership Protocol 0 (TO0) - Registers the device owner with a Rendezvous Server.

- Transfer Ownership Protocol 1 (TO1) - Enables the device to discover its owner via the Rendezvous Server.
- Transfer Ownership Protocol 2 (TO2) - Establishes mutual trust between the device and the final owner, completing the onboarding process .

These stages progressively establish trust, verify device identity, and complete the secure provisioning of configuration parameters and policies. The architecture supports mutual authentication and confidentiality via standard mechanisms such as Elliptic Curve Diffie-Hellman (ECDH), digital signatures, and token-based device attestation. Moreover, the protocol is designed to operate securely even when intermediaries like retailers or logistics providers are untrusted, a key differentiator from many legacy onboarding models [1].

One of the key implementation benefits of FDO is its flexibility. Devices can be manufactured at scale without knowing their final deployment context, and ownership can be delegated at any point during the logistics or installation phase. This reduces the operational burden for device integrators and operators, while also minimizing the risk associated with pre-installed credentials. Additionally, the standardization of FDO by the FIDO Alliance has resulted in a reference implementation known as `pri-fidoiot`, which serves as the foundation for the experimental environment used in this project.

The adoption of FDO represents a significant advancement in secure and scalable IoT device onboarding. By decoupling manufacturing from device ownership and leveraging cryptographic ownership transfer, FDO reduces onboarding complexity, mitigates security threats, and enhances operational efficiency in large-scale IoT deployments [1].

2.2.1 Challenges and Limitations of FDO

Despite its strengths, FDO does not directly address how a device should behave once onboarded. It ensures that a device reaches a trusted owner, but it does not provide mechanisms to restrict or govern its communication patterns after deployment. Some technical and operational challenges that FDO have to faces are the folowings:

- *Centralized reliance on Rendezvous Servers.* The onboarding process depends on the availability of a trusted third-party server. If this server is compromised, adversaries may redirect devices to malicious owners [1].
 - *Lack of post-quantum cryptography support.* FDO currently relies on elliptic curve cryptography, which may be vulnerable to future quantum attacks. Emerging cryptographic standards such as CRYSTALS-Kyber could enhance security [1].
 - *Limited support for lifecycle security.* While FDO secures the onboarding phase, it does not provide ongoing security enforcement after deployment. Integrating Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) policies could help extend protection across the device lifecycle.
 - *Challenges in untrusted environments.* Although FDO introduces ownership transfer capabilities, securely onboarding devices in untrusted installers or third-party logistics environments remains a concern [1].
-

2.3 Secure Bootstrapping & Lifecycle Security Mechanisms

In the context of connected devices, security cannot be limited to the onboarding phase alone. Once a device is authenticated and deployed, it becomes part of a dynamic and often heterogeneous environment where threats can evolve rapidly. Secure bootstrapping refers to the broader process of not only initializing trust at deployment, but also establishing the foundational security configurations that govern the device's ongoing operation. This includes the application of access control policies, the ability to receive and verify updates, and mechanisms to adapt to new security requirements over time.

Lifecycle security mechanisms extend this concept further by ensuring that devices remain trustworthy throughout their operational lifetime. From initial onboarding to eventual decommissioning, it is essential to monitor device behavior, respond to vulnerabilities, and enforce network-level restrictions based on contextual risk. Several frameworks and standards—such as MUD and its extensions—have been proposed to support this continuous enforcement.

2.3.1 Introduction to Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD)

The *Manufacturer Usage Description* (MUD) [3] is a framework introduced by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) in *RFC 8520* to enhance the security of IoT devices by restricting their network behavior according to predefined manufacturer specifications. MUD is designed to mitigate network-based threats, particularly for IoT devices with limited security capabilities, by specifying which network communications are necessary for a device's operation and blocking all others.

According to *NIST Special Publication 1800-15* [2], MUD provides an automated mechanism to define, distribute, and enforce security policies for IoT devices in home and small-business networks. By leveraging MUD, organizations can prevent unauthorized communications that could lead to device compromise or exploitation in cyberattacks such as distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks .

The MUD framework offers a compelling approach to addressing a fundamental challenge in IoT security: the enforcement of access control based on a device's intended behavior. Unlike traditional devices, IoT endpoints are often resource-constrained, lack user interfaces, and are deployed in unmanaged environments where applying fine-grained security policies is difficult. MUD responds to this challenge by allowing manufacturers to publish a formal description of the legitimate network interactions each device type is expected to perform.

By relying on MUD files, network administrators can automate the application of tailored access control rules as soon as a device connects to the network. These rules specify the allowed communication endpoints, protocols, and services, effectively reducing the device's attack surface. The enforcement of such policies ensures that even if a device is compromised or behaves unexpectedly, its network interactions remain constrained within predefined and audited boundaries.

MUD also simplifies policy deployment by eliminating the need for manual rule creation and maintenance, which is particularly valuable in large-scale or heterogeneous IoT networks. It enables consistent security posture enforcement across devices from different vendors, as long as they publish compliant MUD files. Furthermore, the integration of MUD with Software

Defined Networking (SDN) or firewall controllers allows for real-time enforcement of dynamic rules, making it a scalable solution.

From a regulatory and operational perspective, adopting MUD helps organizations align with best practices in zero-trust architecture, least privilege principles, and compliance with emerging cybersecurity frameworks. In the context of lifecycle security, MUD serves not only as a means of initial device profiling but also as a baseline for detecting anomalies, integrating with threat detection systems, and supporting incident response.

In summary, MUD provides a practical, vendor-agnostic mechanism to codify and enforce IoT device behavior, offering security benefits that extend beyond the onboarding phase and into the full operational life of the device.

2.3.2 MUD Architecture and Workflow

The MUD architecture includes several critical components that collectively enable automated policy enforcement and device-specific access control for IoT networks. These components, based on the NIST SP 1800-15 reference model[2], are illustrated on Figure 2.2 and described as follows:

Figure 2.2: FDO Onboarding Process Sequence Diagram

- **MUD File:** A standardized, digitally signed file that specifies the network communications required by a device to function as intended. It defines acceptable protocols, destinations, and services and is authored by the device manufacturer.
- **MUD File Server:** A server hosting the MUD file and its associated signature, typically operated by the manufacturer. Network components fetch the file from this location to apply its rules.
- **MUD Manager:** A logical network component responsible for retrieving, verifying, and interpreting the MUD file. It transforms the file into device-specific access control policies and interacts with enforcement points.
- **Router/Switch/SDN:** The enforcement point that applies the access control rules

derived from the MUD file. It restricts communications for each device to only what is explicitly permitted in the file, rejecting all other traffic.

- **IoT Device:** A MUD-capable endpoint that emits or makes available a MUD URL, either through DHCP options, LLDP, embedded certificate extensions, or during secure onboarding.

The interaction among these components follows a standardized sequence:

1. The IoT device presents its MUD URL during onboarding or network connection (e.g., via DHCP or LLDP).
2. The MUD Manager retrieves the MUD file and its digital signature from the MUD File Server.
3. After verifying the signature, the MUD Manager parses the file, converts it into access control policies and enforces the policies.
4. The Router/Switch/SDN applies these rules, restricting the device's network behavior to its intended operational scope.

This automated process minimizes manual configuration errors and enhances security posture by ensuring that each device operates within its intended configuration scope.

2.3.3 Limitations of MUD

Despite its advantages, MUD has several limitations that impact its effectiveness in secure bootstrapping and lifecycle security:

- **Limited policy granularity:** MUD primarily focuses on network-layer access control and lacks support for more advanced security models such as role-based access control (RBAC) or attribute-based access control (ABAC).
- **Dependency on manufacturer support:** The effectiveness of MUD depends on device manufacturers providing accurate and updated MUD files. Inconsistent adoption or poorly defined policies can undermine security.
- **Scalability challenges:** Managing and enforcing individual MUD policies across large-scale IoT deployments can introduce administrative complexity.

Threat MUD: Enhancing MUD with Dynamic Threat Response

Threat MUD is an enhancement of the Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) framework designed to enable rapid and automated responses to newly discovered security vulnerabilities affecting IoT devices. Unlike standard MUD, which enforces predefined static network policies, Threat MUD introduces a mechanism for updating security configurations dynamically when threats emerge [2].

Threat MUD Process and Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) Integration

Threat MUD enhances IoT security by allowing security updates and mitigations to be distributed via CTI platforms, such as the Malware Information Sharing Platform (MISP). This allows security researchers, network operators, and device manufacturers to collaboratively respond to threats in a structured manner.

The process of implementing Threat MUD follows these steps:

1. A new security vulnerability affecting an IoT device model is discovered. This vulnerability may be identified by:
 - The device manufacturer during routine security assessments.
 - A security researcher or network operator detecting unusual activity.
 - Automated monitoring tools or threat intelligence feeds reporting exploitation attempts.
2. The information about the vulnerability is shared via a CTI platform, using structured threat intelligence formats like STIX (Structured Threat Information eXpression).
3. The device manufacturer or a trusted security entity generates a Threat MUD file that contains specific mitigations for the vulnerability. These mitigations could include for example:
 - Firmware updates or software patches.
 - Network access restrictions, such as blocking malicious domains or ports.
 - Cryptographic suite updates, replacing weak encryption algorithms.
 - Temporary quarantine measures for potentially compromised devices.
4. A Threat MUD URL is published on the CTI platform alongside the vulnerability description. This URL points to the Threat MUD file, allowing network security solutions to retrieve and apply the mitigations.
5. The Threat MUD Manager in the network retrieves the Threat MUD file and processes the defined security policies.
6. The Threat MUD Enforcer applies the new security policies, ensuring that affected devices are protected against the identified vulnerability.

By integrating Threat MUD with CTI, organizations can establish a real-time vulnerability response system, ensuring that new threats are automatically mitigated with minimal manual intervention.

Threat MUD Architecture

NIST SP 1800-15 introduces Threat MUD as an extension to the MUD framework designed to block communications with domains and IPs associated with known threats. Unlike traditional MUD files, which describe allowed communications for a specific device model, Threat MUD files describe external entities that should be denied for all devices. The process relies

on DNS response monitoring and integration with threat intelligence providers. The main components are:

- **Threat Agent:** Embedded in the local router, this component monitors DNS responses for null results. When it detects a failed resolution, it queries a threat-signaling API to determine whether the domain is associated with a known threat.
- **Threat API:** A remote service that confirms whether a domain has been flagged as dangerous, and if so, provides the name of the threat intelligence provider and how to locate the associated Threat MUD file.
- **Threat MUD File Server:** A server managed by a threat intelligence provider that hosts Threat MUD files. These files list all known malicious domains and IP addresses associated with a specific threat campaign.
- **Threat MUD File:** A signed JSON file formatted like a MUD file, but instead of specifying permitted behavior for a device, it lists external communication targets (domains/IPs) that should be blocked for all network devices. It is threat-scoped, not device-scoped.
- **Threat MUD Manager:** A component that retrieves, verifies, and parses the Threat MUD file. It configures both the firewall and DNS to block access to all domains/IPs listed.
- **Enforcement Points:** The router's firewall and local DNS service. The firewall blocks traffic to the listed destinations, while the DNS service returns null responses for listed domains, preventing resolution attempts.

Advantages and Limitations of Threat MUD

Threat MUD extends the original MUD framework by introducing the ability to dynamically adapt security policies in response to emerging threats. One of its main advantages lies in its capacity to enable proactive defense mechanisms. Instead of relying solely on static definitions of allowed behavior, Threat MUD allows manufacturers or network administrators to issue updated policies when a vulnerability is discovered or when malicious activity is detected. This allows the network to respond in near real time to incidents by reconfiguring access controls, isolating vulnerable devices, or enforcing remediation steps such as firmware updates or cryptographic suite changes.

Another important benefit of Threat MUD is its compatibility with existing MUD infrastructure. It builds upon the same architectural model—comprising MUD managers, MUD file servers. This makes it relatively easy to deploy in environments already supporting MUD, while significantly increasing the system's resilience to evolving threats. Moreover, Threat MUD encourages a collaborative approach to security by leveraging CTI platforms like MISP, enabling the coordinated distribution of updated policy URLs associated with specific vulnerabilities or attack campaigns.

Despite these advantages, several limitations affect the current maturity and adoption of Threat MUD. One of the main challenges is the lack of standardized procedures for generating, validating, and distributing Threat MUD files. As it stands, there is no formal specification

governing how these files should be created or what trust anchors should be used to verify their authenticity. This creates potential risks in environments where malicious or incorrect threat policies could be injected into the network infrastructure.

In addition, the enforcement of dynamically updated policies requires a reliable and secure communication channel between CTI platforms, MUD managers, and enforcement points. Any compromise or misconfiguration along this chain could result in delays, incorrect policy application, or even denial of service due to overly aggressive policy blocking. Furthermore, the effectiveness of Threat MUD relies heavily on timely intelligence and manufacturer support. If vendors fail to publish Threat MUD updates for known vulnerabilities, affected devices may remain exposed even in well-managed networks.

Another limitation is operational: frequent or aggressive policy updates could introduce instability in large-scale deployments, particularly if updates are not properly validated or tested. Network administrators must also manage potential conflicts between existing MUD rules and new threat-based directives, ensuring that the overall policy set remains coherent and does not inadvertently block legitimate services.

In summary, Threat MUD represents a promising evolution of the MUD framework, adding essential capabilities for dynamic threat mitigation. However, to realize its full potential, future work is needed to address standardization gaps, ensure trustworthy update mechanisms, and provide integration guidelines that minimize operational risk while maximizing security responsiveness.

Despite these challenges, Threat MUD represents a major advancement in IoT security, providing an automated, intelligence-driven approach to mitigating device vulnerabilities.

3 Targets analysis and methodology

3.1 Targets analysis

The analysis focuses on evaluating the security and operational effectiveness of integrating FIDO Device Onboard (FDO) for secure onboarding and Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) for lifecycle security. The study aims to assess vulnerabilities, limitations, and potential improvements in secure device provisioning, policy enforcement, and lifecycle protection.

Technical Scope

The scope of the analysis includes five main components:

1. The FIDO FDO onboarding process, using the official `pri-fidoiot` implementation.
2. A custom Python-based MUD framework for enforcing access control policies.
3. Threat MUD extensions for dynamic security updates based on real-time threat intelligence.
4. Integration of both systems in a testbed of simulated IoT devices.
5. Security evaluation throughout the device's lifecycle, from onboarding to policy adaptation.

Each of these components is examined individually and in combination, with a particular focus on interoperability, scalability, and resilience to attacks.

Onboarding Security Assessment

A core objective of this study is to analyze the security of the onboarding process using FIDO FDO. The FDO protocol aims to remove traditional onboarding weaknesses by introducing cryptographic ownership delegation. Instead of configuring a device during manufacturing with static credentials or predefined cloud endpoints, FDO allows ownership to be assigned later, during deployment. This concept, known as "late binding", reduces risks in the supply chain and simplifies device integration in varied environments.

Security in FDO is established through a sequence of ownership transfer protocols (TO0, TO1, TO2), verified by digital signatures and certificates. The analysis in this work evaluates the resistance of this process to common attacks such as impersonation, man-in-the-middle, and replay. Particular attention is given to the use of ownership vouchers and the trust assumptions placed on the rendezvous server.

The following aspects will be evaluated:

- Resistance to **man-in-the-middle (MitM) attacks** during ownership transfer.
- Strength of **cryptographic mechanisms**, including elliptic curve-based authentication and ownership voucher verification.
- Potential **replay attack scenarios** exploiting unsecured ownership handshakes.
- The effectiveness of **rendezvous server authentication and redirection** mechanisms.

Lifecycle Security and MUD Policy Enforcement

Beyond onboarding, the study assesses the ability of MUD to enforce security throughout the device lifecycle. Key aspects include:

- Ability to **restrict unauthorized network access** through predefined MUD policies.
- Effectiveness of **dynamic policy updates** via Threat MUD to mitigate new vulnerabilities.
- Scalability of **policy enforcement** across multiple devices in an enterprise or industrial IoT environment.

Integration Challenges and Limitations

The research also identifies challenges in integrating FDO with MUD, including:

- **Interoperability issues:** Differences in how FDO and MUD define security policies and enforce access control.
- **Latency concerns:** The impact of onboarding and policy retrieval on device activation time.
- **Policy conflicts:** Potential inconsistencies between predefined MUD rules and dynamic Threat MUD updates.

3.2 Methodology

This section presents the research methodology used to analyze the integration of FIDO Device Onboard (FDO) for secure onboarding and Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) for lifecycle security. The objective is to evaluate the security and operational effectiveness of combining these frameworks, addressing their strengths and limitations.

3.2.1 Research Approach

The study follows an experimental research approach, focusing on:

- Implementing FIDO Device Onboard (FDO) for secure onboarding using the open-source repository `pri-fidoiot` provided by the FIDO Alliance [6].
-

- Developing a custom Python-based MUD framework, which will be responsible for defining and enforcing security policies post-onboarding.
- Conducting security evaluations to identify vulnerabilities and analyze the integration challenges of FDO and MUD.

3.2.2 Evaluation Metrics

To assess the security and performance of the integration, the following evaluation metrics will be used:

- Onboarding security. Evaluating the strength of FDO's authentication mechanisms, including ownership vouchers and cryptographic binding.
- Bootstrapping time. Measuring the time required for device registration and ownership transfer.
- Policy enforcement effectiveness. Testing the ability of the MUD implementation to restrict unauthorized network activity.
- Scalability. Assessing how well the integrated system handles multiple simultaneous device onboardings and policy applications.
- Lifecycle security. Analyzing the ability of MUD to enforce security updates, network restrictions, and policy adjustments dynamically.

3.2.3 Experimental Setup

The experiments will be conducted in a controlled testbed to evaluate the secure onboarding and lifecycle security mechanisms.

Testbed Environment

The experimental setup consists of:

- IoT devices. Simulated IoT endpoints representing constrained devices, deployed in a sandboxed environment.
 - FIDO FDO Server. A deployment of the `pri-fidoiot` implementation, acting as the onboarding infrastructure.
 - Rendezvous Server. A component used by FDO to establish device ownership transfers securely.
 - MUD Manager (Custom Implementation). A Python-based MUD server responsible for retrieving and enforcing MUD policies.
 - MUD Policy Storage. A database maintaining predefined and dynamically updated MUD policies.
 - Threat MUD Integration. An extension that enables dynamic policy updates in response to new vulnerabilities.
-

Onboarding and Security Policy Enforcement Workflow

The workflow for integrating FIDO FDO and MUD-based lifecycle security consists of the following steps:

1. The IoT device initiates onboarding using FIDO FDO, contacting the Rendezvous Server to retrieve ownership credentials.
2. The device establishes trust with the FDO Server, and ownership transfer is completed.
3. Upon successful onboarding, the FDO Server provides the device MUD URL to the MUD Manager, which retrieves its security policy.
4. The MUD Enforcer applies access control rules based on the policy, restricting network interactions.
5. If a security threat is detected, a Threat MUD File is generated and distributed dynamically via the MUD Manager.
6. The updated MUD policy is enforced, ensuring continuous lifecycle security.

Security and Performance Testing

Security evaluations will include:

- Evaluating the effectiveness of MUD in preventing unauthorized communications.
- Measuring the impact of Threat MUD updates on security enforcement and device response times.
- Probe the effectiveness integration of FDO and MUD workflow.

3.2.4 Expected Contributions

The integration of FIDO FDO and MUD aims to establish a secure, automated, and adaptive IoT security framework. This research will:

- Demonstrate the feasibility of combining onboarding and policy enforcement for improved IoT security.
 - Identify the strengths and limitations of FDO and MUD in real-world deployment scenarios.
 - Provide insights into enhancing MUD with dynamic threat response capabilities.
-

4 Design and Implementation

This section presents the full technical implementation of the secure onboarding and lifecycle policy enforcement system proposed in this work. Building on the foundations explored in previous sections—specifically the onboarding mechanisms offered by FDO and the behavioral policy enforcement of MUD, this section details how both are integrated into a coherent and operational security framework. The implementation connects all phases of the device lifecycle, from manufacturing to deployment, onboarding, and continuous policy governance.

4.1 System Architecture Overview

Figure 4.1: Complete Architectural flow for FDO, MUD and Threat MUD

The complete system implementation is structured around two sequential and complementary phases: the secure onboarding and static policy enforcement phase using FDO and MUD, and the dynamic policy update phase enabled by Threat MUD. These phases cover the full security lifecycle of an IoT device, from the initial moment it is deployed and trusted, to its ongoing protection against emerging threats. Figure 4.1 illustrates the full architecture and the division between onboarding and adaptive security operations.

4.1.1 Phase 1: Secure Onboarding and Policy Enforcement (FDO + MUD)

The first phase begins with the manufacturer provisioning the device during the FDO DI stage. This includes embedding cryptographic credentials and a reference to a rendezvous

server. Additionally, the manufacturer hosts the MUD file describing the device's expected communication behavior on a dedicated MUD File Server.

Once the device is deployed, it initiates onboarding by contacting the Rendezvous Server (FDO TO1). Meanwhile, the operator or owner registers its ownership intent and corresponding Owner Server endpoint during FDO TO0. The rendezvous phase completes with the device obtaining the Owner Server's IP, initiating the secure ownership transfer protocol (FDO TO2), which involves mutual authentication and provisioning of deployment-specific metadata.

After successful onboarding, the Owner Server sends the MUD URL associated with the device to the MUD Manager. The MUD Manager is responsible for retrieving the MUD file and verifying its digital signature to ensure its authenticity. Upon validation, the policy is parsed and translated into enforceable network rules, which are applied by the Domain Orchestrator. This step ensures that the device is only permitted to communicate in accordance with its declared behavior, as defined by the manufacturer.

4.1.2 Phase 2: Threat MUD and Dynamic Policy Response

While MUD provides a static and manufacturer-defined policy baseline, real-world security demands require the ability to update these policies in response to evolving threats. The second phase introduces the Threat MUD mechanism, which enables the injection of dynamic policies when vulnerabilities are discovered after deployment.

When a new threat is identified—either by the manufacturer or an external threat intelligence source—the information is first processed through a CTI platform such as MISP. The manufacturer then generates a Threat MUD file containing updated access control rules or mitigation actions, such as blocking known malicious domains or enforcing protocol restrictions. This file is published on a Threat MUD File Server along with a digital signature.

The Threat MUD Manager, operating within the owner domain, receives the threat event (step 2) and retrieves the Threat MUD file and its signature from the manufacturer (step 4). Once the signature is validated (step 5), the policy is forwarded to the Threat MUD Enforcer (step 6), which applies the updated rules within the network infrastructure.

As in the MUD case, the Threat MUD file is also converted into an actionable policy and shared with the Domain Orchestrator to ensure consistent policy interpretation across domains and systems (step 7). This integration allows the system to adapt dynamically to new risks without requiring manual reconfiguration, preserving automation and minimizing reaction time.

Together, these two phases offer a layered and resilient security model. FDO provides strong trust anchors for initial onboarding, MUD enforces manufacturer-declared behavior, and Threat MUD introduces reactivity and adaptability—forming a continuous security chain that protects the device throughout its lifecycle.

4.2 FDO Implementation – Secure Onboarding

The foundation of this architecture is built upon the FDO protocol, which provides a standardized and secure method for zero-touch onboarding of IoT devices. The goal of the onboarding phase is to securely transfer ownership of a device from the manufacturer to the

operator, while embedding critical information needed for subsequent security enforcement—such as the MUD URL.

Figure 4.2 illustrates the main stages of this onboarding process. It begins during the Device Initialization (DI) phase, where the manufacturer provisions the device with cryptographic credentials, a reference to the rendezvous server, and—in this implementation—a preconfigured MUD URL. By embedding the MUD URL at this stage, the device can later inform the owner about its intended network behavior in an automated and verifiable way.

Once deployed, the device connects to the rendezvous server to begin the ownership transfer process. This involves FDO TO1, during which the device identifies itself and requests the endpoint of its designated Owner Server. In parallel, the operator has already registered with the rendezvous server via FDO TO0, declaring its willingness to assume ownership of the specific device.

In the final step of the onboarding process (FDO TO2), the device and Owner Server establish mutual trust through cryptographic exchanges. During this stage, the ownership voucher is validated and the device receives deployment-specific instructions. Crucially, the Owner Server also receives the MUD URL that was injected during the DI phase. This ensures that, immediately after onboarding, the owner can fetch the corresponding MUD file and enforce behavioral constraints without requiring manual intervention or additional device-side configuration.

This design leverages the modularity of FDO to not only automate secure onboarding but also serve as a transport channel for conveying post-deployment security metadata—such as the MUD reference. By integrating this information early in the lifecycle, the transition from onboarding to policy enforcement becomes seamless and robust.

Figure 4.2: FDO onboarding flow with MUD URL delivery during ownership transfer

Reference Implementation: `pri-fidoiot`

To realize the onboarding workflow described above, the open-source reference implementation of FDO provided by the FIDO Alliance was used ¹.

¹<https://github.com/fido-device-onboard/pri-fidoiot>

The services were launched using the official `docker-compose.yml` provided in the repository. Configuration files were customized to inject the MUD URL into the device metadata during DI. Additionally, cryptographic keys were pre-generated using the tools bundled in the project, and the ownership vouchers were signed with the Manufacturer's key and stored in the appropriate registry for retrieval during the onboarding session.

A minimal reproducible setup was defined with the following command:

Listing 4.1: Launching pri-fidoiot with Docker Compose

```
1 git clone https://github.com/fido-device-onboard/pri-fidoiot.git
2 cd pri-fidoiot/pri-fidoiot/component-samples/demo/aio
3 docker compose up --build
4 cd pri-fidoiot/pri-fidoiot/component-samples/demo/device
5 docker compose up --build
```

This commands initializes the full onboarding stack: Manufacturer, Rendezvous, Owner, and Device services. Once running, the simulated device initiates onboarding, and the MUD URL is transmitted as part of the TO2 payload. The Owner Server then passes this URL to the MUD Manager for policy retrieval and enforcement, as described in the next section.

4.3 MUD Policy Enforcement

Figure 4.3: FDO-based onboarding and MUD policy enforcement flow

Once the device has been successfully onboarded through the FDO protocol and the ownership has been transferred to the operator, the next critical step is to establish runtime control over the device's network behavior. This is achieved through the MUD framework, which enables

the automatic retrieval and enforcement of security policies defined by the manufacturer. These policies constrain the device’s network activity to what is strictly necessary for its legitimate operation.

The MUD integration begins at the end of the FDO TO2 phase, when the Owner Server receives the MUD URL associated with the device. This URL, which was injected during the Device Initialization phase by the manufacturer, points to a JSON-formatted MUD file hosted on a MUD File Server under the manufacturer’s control. The Owner Server forwards this URL to the MUD Manager, which is responsible for orchestrating the policy enforcement workflow.

The MUD Manager performs several key functions. First, it retrieves the MUD file and its associated digital signature. Authenticity and integrity are then verified using the manufacturer’s public key. This validation step is crucial to prevent malicious actors from substituting or tampering with the policy definitions. Once verified, the MUD file is parsed according to the IETF RFC 8520 schema.

The MUD file contains definitions for allowed communication behaviors. These are typically expressed in terms of permitted protocols, DNS names, and ports. For example, a smart sensor may be permitted to contact only a specific cloud endpoint over HTTPS, while being blocked from accessing local or peer-to-peer services. These policy elements are then translated into actionable policy. This allows the policy to be integrated into a higher-level orchestration framework, referred to here as the Domain Orchestrator. The orchestrator maintains a global view of active device policies and enables auditing, conflict resolution, and lifecycle management at a system-wide level.

In this implementation, a simplified Domain Orchestrator is used to directly generate and apply iptables commands based on the parsed MUD entries. This approach supports rapid prototyping and validation of enforcement logic while maintaining a clear path to integration with more scalable enforcement engines (e.g., via SDN controllers or enterprise firewalls).

The combination of policy validation, rule generation, and centralized orchestration ensures that the device is immediately placed under a set of strict behavioral constraints that reflect the manufacturer’s intended operation. This significantly reduces the attack surface of the device and prevents unauthorized or anomalous communications from occurring—even in the event of partial device compromise.

By delegating enforcement to infrastructure-level components and automating the entire retrieval and validation pipeline, the system aligns with the principles of zero-trust networking and least privilege. More importantly, it enables seamless transition from onboarding to continuous security enforcement, ensuring that device behavior is predictable, auditable, and bounded from the first moment of deployment.

4.3.1 Interpreting a MUD File

The MUD file used in this implementation corresponds to a Siemens IoT device model 10294230 and is hosted at the specified URL . This file follows the IETF MUD specification (RFC 8520) [3] and serves as the basis for defining the legitimate communication behavior expected from the device. Unlike in previous architectural versions, the MUD Manager in this implementation no longer acts as the enforcer. The key elements defined in the file are:

- **Metadata:** The file declares general information such as `mud-version`, `last-update`,
-

`modelname`, and `systeminfo`, which describe the versioning and identity of the device. The `is-supported` flag confirms that the device adheres to MUD principles.

- **Policy Segmentation:** The file includes two main sections — `from-device-policy` and `to-device-policy` — each referencing a corresponding ACL list. These sections organize the rules depending on whether traffic is initiated by or directed to the device.
- **Access Control Lists (ACLs):** Each ACL defines one or more Access Control Entries (ACEs) that specify permitted communications. For example, ACL `mud-76100-v6fr` includes a rule allowing the device to initiate outbound TCP connections to the domain `test.example.com` on port 443. Similarly, ACL `mud-76100-v6to` defines permitted inbound connections from the same domain on the same port.
- **Rule Structure:** Each ACE includes fields such as DNS-based domain names (`ietf-acldns`), protocol numbers, and port matching operators. The `direction-initiated` field in the TCP match indicates the directionality of the traffic, ensuring unidirectional enforcement as required by the device’s operational context. All rules specify the `accept` action to denote allowed traffic.

Listing 4.2: Sample MUD file

```
1 {
2   "ietf-mud:mud": {
3     "mud-version": 1,
4     "mud-url": "https://devicemanufacturer.com/Siemens/10294230/mud.json",
5     "last-update": "2024-12-18T21:07:00+01:00",
6     "cache-validity": 48,
7     "is-supported": true,
8     "modelname": "Siemens",
9     "systeminfo": "Siemens model 10294230 device Current MUD File",
10    "from-device-policy": {
11      "access-lists": {
12        "access-list": [
13          { "name": "mud-76100-v6fr" }
14        ]
15      }
16    },
17    "to-device-policy": {
18      "access-lists": {
19        "access-list": [
20          { "name": "mud-76100-v6to" }
21        ]
22      }
23    }
24  },
25  "ietf-access-control-list:acls": {
26    "acl": [
27      {
28        "name": "mud-76100-v6to",
29        "type": "ipv6-acl-type",
```

```
30     "aces": {
31       "ace": [
32         {
33           "name": "cl0-todev",
34           "matches": {
35             "ipv6": {
36               "ietf-acldns:src-dnsname": "malicious-domain.com",
37               "protocol": 6
38             },
39             "tcp": {
40               "ietf-mud:direction-initiated": "from-device",
41               "source-port": {
42                 "operator": "eq",
43                 "port": 443
44               }
45             }
46           },
47           "actions": { "forwarding": "accept" }
48         }
49       ]
50     },
51     {
52       "name": "mud-76100-v6fr",
53       "type": "ipv6-acl-type",
54       "aces": {
55         "ace": [
56           {
57             "name": "cl0-frdev",
58             "matches": {
59               "ipv6": {
60                 "ietf-acldns:dst-dnsname": "malicious-domain.com",
61                 "protocol": 6
62               },
63               "tcp": {
64                 "ietf-mud:direction-initiated": "from-device",
65                 "destination-port": {
66                   "operator": "eq",
67                   "port": 443
68                 }
69               }
70             },
71             "actions": { "forwarding": "accept" }
72           }
73         ]
74       }
75     }
76   ]
77 }
78 }
79 }
```

4.3.2 Explanation of the Policy

The policy section of the MUD file defines the specific network communications permitted for the device, following a declarative structure organized around access control lists (ACLs). In this example, the MUD file defines two logical policy blocks: `from-device-policy` and `to-device-policy`, each referencing a corresponding ACL name.

The `from-device-policy` block points to the ACL named `mud-76100-v6fr`, which contains a single Access Control Entry (ACE) called `cl0-frdev`. This rule authorizes the device to initiate outbound TCP connections to the domain `test.example.com` using port 443 (commonly associated with HTTPS). The matching conditions are specified in terms of protocol number (TCP), DNS-based destination domain, and the specific destination port. Additionally, the rule includes the `direction-initiated` field set to `from-device`, indicating that only traffic initiated by the device is allowed under this policy.

The action associated with this ACE is to **accept** the matched traffic. This type of rule enables a precise and minimal communication pattern, tightly scoped to a known destination and service. The use of DNS-based identifiers allows the policy to remain valid even if the IP address behind the domain changes over time.

After parsing the policy, the MUD Manager translates the logical rule into an enforcement-compatible format and forwards it to the Domain Orchestrator. The orchestrator, acting as the centralized policy enforcer, applies the rule to the network infrastructure using technologies such as `iptables` or SDN flow entries.

This process demonstrates how MUD policies provide a structured and vendor-declared mechanism for controlling IoT device behavior, ensuring minimal network exposure and reducing the attack surface from the outset.

4.3.3 Example Rule Generation

Once the MUD Manager retrieves and parses the MUD file, it processes the list of ACLs and their Access Control Entries (ACEs) to generate concrete policy rules. These are then sent to the Domain Orchestrator, which is responsible for enforcing the access control rules across the network infrastructure. The following example illustrates the transformation process.

The selected ACE corresponds to the ACL named `mud-76100-v6fr`, where the rule `cl0-frdev` authorizes outbound TCP connections initiated by the device toward the domain `malicious-domain.com` on port 443 (HTTPS). The original entry in the MUD file is:

Listing 4.3: Example MUD rule in JSON format

```
1 {
2     "name": "mud-76100-v6fr",
3     "type": "ipv6-acl-type",
4     "aces": {
5         "ace": [
6             {
7                 "name": "cl0-frdev",
8                 "matches": {
9                     "ipv6": {
10                        "ietf-acldns:dst-dnsname": "malicious-domain.com",
11                        "protocol": 6
```

```
12     },
13     "tcp": {
14         "ietf-mud:direction-initiated": "from-device",
15         "destination-port": {
16             "operator": "eq",
17             "port": 443
18         }
19     }
20 },
21 "actions": {
22     "forwarding": "accept"
23 }
24 }
25 ]
26 }
27 }
```

This rule is automatically translated by the MUD Manager into an equivalent iptables command for enforcement on the local firewall, for this we have to resolve the domain `malicious-domain.com` into the actual IP (e.g., `155.54.201.87`):

Listing 4.4: Translated iptables rule

```
1 iptables -A FORWARD -s <device_ip> -d 155.54.201.87 -p tcp --dport 443 -j ←
   ↪ ACCEPT
```

4.4 Threat MUD and Dynamic Policy Updates

Although MUD provides a structured and scalable mechanism to define the intended network behavior of IoT devices, it is not designed to react immediately to specific security incidents. MUD files can be updated throughout a device's lifecycle—particularly if a manufacturer revises the intended behavior or adds functionality—but these updates are typically declarative and behavior-driven rather than incident-driven.

To fill this gap, the Threat MUD extension has been proposed as a reactive enhancement to the MUD model. Threat MUD allows manufacturers or trusted authorities to publish specialized mitigation policies in response to identified security threats affecting specific devices or firmware versions. These threat-specific policies are not meant to redefine general device behavior, but to overlay targeted restrictions or protections that neutralize or reduce the impact of an active or discovered vulnerability.

Figure 4.4: Threat MUD architecture for dynamic policy update and enforcement

Figure 4.4 illustrates the architecture developed in this work to support Threat MUD. The process begins when a security vulnerability is discovered—either by the manufacturer, a network operator, or a third-party security researcher. This information is disseminated using a CTI platform such as MISP, which announces the threat and references the affected device (e.g., via its MUD URL or unique identifier).

The manufacturer or operator then prepares a Threat MUD file containing updated access control rules or mitigations tailored to the vulnerability. This file may include new restrictions, such as blocking communication with specific domains or IP addresses, disabling known-vulnerable services, or isolating the device from external networks. The file is published on a Threat MUD File Server and signed digitally to ensure authenticity.

The Threat MUD Manager within the owner domain periodically monitors threat feeds or receives event-based alerts from the CTI platform. When a relevant Threat MUD reference is detected, it downloads the file, verifies the signature, and translate the new rules into actionable rules. These are propagated to the Domain Orchestrator for unified policy oversight and coordination.

Unlike the standard MUD file, which describes permitted behavior from the perspective of normal operation, the Threat MUD file is reactive by design. It focuses on what must be denied or reconfigured as a result of a known security risk. This distinction allows for a clear separation of concerns: MUD governs what a device is allowed to do; Threat MUD governs what a device must stop doing due to a detected vulnerability.

In the implementation developed for this work, the threat intelligence exchange is modeled in a simplified but realistic way. Instead of pulling full threat feeds or parsing structured STIX messages, the CTI platform sends a POST request directly to the Threat MUD Manager, containing the identifier of the detected threat. This identifier corresponds to a unique Threat ID associated with a specific vulnerability or security event.

Upon receiving this POST message, the Threat MUD Manager constructs the Threat MUD URL using a predefined and mutually agreed server base path. The resulting URL points to a Threat MUD file stored by the manufacturer or security provider, typically in a format similar to standard MUD but with threat-specific restrictions. The Threat MUD Manager retrieves the file, verifies its digital signature, and triggers the policy update process, forwarding the new rules to the Domain Orchestrator.

This implementation balances realism and simplicity. It avoids the overhead of deep CTI parsing while still supporting automated threat-based policy enforcement, enabling fast and focused response to known vulnerabilities with minimal delay or manual intervention.

4.4.1 Applying Threat MUD Mitigations Based on Device Inventory

In the proposed architecture, the Domain Orchestrator is responsible not only for enforcing regular MUD policies but also for dynamically applying threat mitigations derived from Threat MUD files. One of the key features of this system is the ability to selectively apply mitigations only to those devices that are known to be affected by a particular threat.

To support this, each Threat MUD file includes a dedicated field named `models-affected`, which enumerates the device models that are vulnerable or impacted by the threat. This allows the orchestrator to compare the threat scope with its internal device inventory. The inventory is maintained as part of the orchestrator's asset management subsystem and contains information such as device identifiers, model names, manufacturers, and onboarding metadata.

When a new Threat MUD file is retrieved and verified, the orchestrator parses the `models-affected` field and iterates over the registered devices in the inventory. For each device, it checks whether its model name matches any of the listed entries. If a match is found, the orchestrator proceeds to apply the mitigations defined in the Threat MUD file to that specific device.

This matching process allows for precise and targeted enforcement of mitigations without impacting unrelated devices. It also supports the dynamic inclusion or removal of mitigations as device inventory changes or new threat information becomes available. This capability is crucial in large-scale IoT networks where device heterogeneity is common and blanket mitigation may lead to unnecessary service disruption.

By decoupling the threat detection (via CTI and Threat MUD retrieval) from enforcement targeting (via model-based inventory filtering), the architecture ensures both responsiveness and precision in mitigating threats across the device lifecycle.

4.5 System Cohesion and Behavior

The implementation presented in this work is not merely a composition of isolated modules, but a cohesive architecture that automates and secures the entire lifecycle of an IoT device—from onboarding, to policy enforcement, to threat-based adaptation. Each phase contributes to a continuous security pipeline where trust, governance, and resilience are maintained without requiring manual reconfiguration or human intervention after initial deployment.

The integration begins with FDO, which ensures secure ownership transfer and trust establishment. Through its modular design, FDO also becomes the mechanism through which

metadata—such as the device’s MUD URL—is delivered to the owner’s domain. This metadata becomes the entry point for the next stage: policy enforcement.

As soon as onboarding is complete, the MUD Manager retrieves the MUD file and applies the manufacturer-defined policies to control the device’s network behavior. These rules are enforced immediately, narrowing the attack surface by allowing only the communications explicitly declared as necessary. This aligns the deployment with least privilege and zero-trust principles from the outset.

The architecture then extends beyond initial policy enforcement by incorporating Threat MUD, which enables dynamic response to security events. When a threat affecting a specific device or firmware version is identified, the CTI system triggers the generation and distribution of a Threat MUD file containing updated mitigation actions. The Threat MUD Manager receives the threat notification, retrieves the corresponding file, validates its authenticity, and seamlessly updates the policy enforcement layer. This feedback loop ensures that policy enforcement remains relevant and responsive throughout the device’s lifecycle.

The Domain Orchestrator plays a central coordinating role. It collects the policies from both MUD and Threat MUD processes, maintains a unified view of the active rules across all devices, and supports auditing, compliance checking, and conflict resolution. In this way, local enforcement decisions remain autonomous and efficient, while global oversight and traceability are preserved.

Taken together, the architecture supports the secure onboarding and operation of IoT devices under changing threat conditions. Devices are automatically trusted at deployment, governed according to known-good behavior, and protected against emerging threats without requiring firmware updates or user intervention. This continuous security posture provides a scalable and standards-based model for deploying and managing secure-by-design IoT infrastructures.

5 Evaluation

This section presents the evaluation of the proposed lifecycle security architecture, focusing on three main aspects: (1) the security pipeline, which includes onboarding and MUD policy enforcement; (2) the dynamic security response provided by Threat MUD; and (3) the overall end-to-end performance and integration of the entire system. Each aspect is evaluated using real execution times extracted from the implemented testbed, with emphasis on automation, modularity, and latency.

The evaluation is not centered on testing the scalability of enforcement rules in a large environment. Instead, the experiments use minimal but realistic configurations (specifically, for constrained devices like IoT environments) to validate the full integration of FDO, MUD, and Threat MUD in a controlled scenario. This allows us to focus on the management of the workflow and the interoperability between components, which is the core contribution of this work.

5.1 Test-bed

To validate the proposed architecture and measure its performance, a dedicated testbed was developed, simulating a realistic but controlled environment in which onboarding, policy enforcement, and threat mitigation operations could be observed and measured.

The testbed includes the full lifecycle security pipeline: the onboarding infrastructure using FDO, the MUD policy enforcement infrastructure, and the dynamic policy update mechanism via Threat MUD. All components were deployed using lightweight containers and executed on a single server to ensure timing consistency and facilitate rapid iteration.

Figure 5.1 illustrates the architecture of the testbed used to validate the integration of FDO and MUD during the device registration process in an organizational IoT environment. The depicted sequence represents the point where devices, having already undergone the DI (Device Initialization) step at the manufacturer's site, are onboarding into the organization's network via the FDO protocol.

Hardware Environment

The experiments were conducted on a Linux workstation with the following characteristics:

- CPU: AMD Ryzen 7 7800X3D @ 4.2GHz
- RAM: 64 GB DDR5
- Storage: 1 TB NVMe SSD
- Operating System: Ubuntu 22.04.3 LTS (64-bit) under WSL2

All services were hosted locally using Docker containers to ensure process isolation while avoiding external network-induced noise in measurements.

Software Stack

The system was implemented using a mix of open-source components and custom services:

- **FDO Implementation:** `pri-fidoiot` (FIDO Alliance) ¹ for onboarding and ownership transfer.
- **MUD Manager:** Developed in Python, using Flask for the REST interface and direct generation of `iptables` rules for enforcement.
- **Threat MUD Manager:** Python-based microservice capable of parsing Threat IDs received via POST messages and retrieving the corresponding Threat MUD file.
- **CTI Simulator:** A minimal threat simulator component that mimics the MISP behavior by sending a POST request to the Threat MUD Manager with a Threat ID.
- **Domain Orchestrator:** A simplified Orchestrator that collects and logs all enforced policies in a centralized structure for inspection and visualization.

Network Simulation

Each device lifecycle was simulated in a self-contained Docker network, with isolated subnets representing the manufacturer domain, the rendezvous server, and the owner domain. This allowed precise emulation of protocol flows between:

- **Manufacturer Server → Device:** Credential and metadata injection via FDO DI.
- **Device → Rendezvous Server:** Discovery of the Owner Server (FDO TO1).
- **Device → Owner Server:** Secure ownership transfer and metadata delivery (FDO TO2).
- **Owner Server → MUD Manager:** MUD URL notification and policy retrieval.
- **CTI → Threat MUD Manager:** Threat alerts via HTTP POST and mitigation activation.

Metrics and Instrumentation

To capture execution times and enforce policy validations, logging hooks were embedded at the boundaries of each protocol phase. Timestamps were extracted at:

- Onboarding request initiation and ownership voucher confirmation (FDO TO0–TO2).
- MUD file retrieval, signature validation, and rule injection.

¹<https://github.com/fido-device-onboard/pri-fidoiot>

Figure 5.1: Test-bed architecture

- Threat MUD POST receipt and policy update confirmation.

Logs were processed using Python scripts to compute averages, distribution, and comparative visualizations included in Section 5.

This modular testbed provided an accurate and reproducible environment for validating the architectural claims and performance characteristics of the proposed secure onboarding and policy lifecycle system.

5.2 MUD Rule Enforcement and Translation Latency

This section analyzes the performance of the MUD enforcement phase after the FDO onboarding completes. Once the device finishes the TO2 step, the Owner Server extracts the MUD URL and initiates a POST request to the MUD Manager, which triggers the retrieval, parsing, and translation of the MUD file. This request introduces a slight delay, but as it involves only a single HTTP POST transaction, its contribution to the overall delay is negligible.

It is important to clarify that each MUD file used in this evaluation defines only two rules: one for outbound traffic and one for inbound traffic. This decision was made deliberately to reduce noise in timing measurements and to shift focus toward validating the interoperability between FDO and the policy manager. Consequently, the results shown here are not meant to demonstrate scalability in terms of rule complexity or quantity. Instead, the emphasis lies in showing that the complete FDO-to-MUD policy application process works reliably and within latency thresholds suitable for constrained environments.

Figure 5.2: Total Time from FDO TO1 to MUD Policy Applied

The first evaluation focuses on measuring the total time required to securely onboard a device and apply its MUD policy. This corresponds to the time between the start of the TO1 phase and the completion of the policy application triggered by the MUD Manager. The experiment was performed over a batch of 20 simulated devices, each configured with a unique MUD file containing two ACL rules defining permitted communication behaviors.

Figure ?? shows the total measured time required to complete the entire lifecycle—from the start of the FDO process (TO1) through the successful application of the MUD policy. The results across a set of 20 distinct device executions demonstrate an average end-to-end completion time of approximately **838 ms**, with a median value of **840 ms**. Individual device times ranged between roughly 600 ms and slightly above 1000 ms, indicating some variability primarily attributable to container scheduling overhead and minor network latency fluctuations within the Docker environment.

The lifecycle latency is further broken down into two distinct phases in Figure ??: the onboarding phase (FDO TO1→TO2) and the policy enforcement phase (MUD retrieval, translation, and enforcement). Here, we observe that the onboarding phase completes in approximately **256 ms**, while the subsequent policy enforcement phase averages around **374 ms**. The enforcement phase includes the slight additional latency introduced by forwarding the MUD URL through a single HTTP POST request from the Owner Server to the MUD Manager. This HTTP transaction introduces minimal delay and does not significantly impact overall performance, demonstrating the feasibility of adding integration points between FDO and external management components with negligible latency penalty.

Figure 5.4 offers a detailed breakdown of the execution times for each phase of the lifecycle

Figure 5.3: End-to-End Lifecycle Security: Execution Time by Phase (Average)

security process across individual devices. Specifically, it distinguishes clearly between the onboarding phase (FDO TO1→TO2, represented in blue) and the MUD policy enforcement phase (MUD Received at MUD Manager→Policy Applied, represented in orange).

The results indicate some variability in execution times across different devices, reflecting minor fluctuations in system load, resource availability, and Docker container scheduling. Despite this variability, the onboarding phase remains relatively consistent across devices, generally around 200–300 ms. Conversely, the policy enforcement phase exhibits greater variability, ranging approximately from 100 ms up to 700 ms. This variability in the enforcement phase primarily stems from the operations involved in retrieving, parsing, translating, and also some network latency within Docker environment.

Device-specific observations also highlight instances such as Device1 and Device5, which present noticeably higher enforcement times compared to the rest. These instances could be attributed to transient container resource constraints or temporary network delays within the testbed environment. Nevertheless, even in these more delayed cases, the total lifecycle completion remains comfortably within sub-second latency, indicating a robust and reliable integration pipeline capable of rapid onboarding and policy enforcement.

Overall, this per-device analysis underscores the consistent performance of the onboarding process (FDO), while also highlighting areas where minor optimizations in the policy enforcement pipeline could further stabilize response times across varying deployment conditions.

Table 5.1 presents a comparative analysis between the proposed FDO and MUD-based approach and other relevant state-of-the-art onboarding and policy enforcement solutions.

The results clearly highlight that the solution developed in this work (FDO + MUD) achieves rapid onboarding and immediate policy enforcement, with an onboarding time of approximately 256 ms and a policy enforcement delay of about 374 ms per MUD, which is

Figure 5.4: End-to-End Lifecycle Execution Time by Device and Phase

Table 5.1: Comparison of Onboarding and Policy Enforcement Times

Approach / Solution	Onboarding Time	Policy Enforcement Time
FDO + MUD	~256 ms	~374 ms
Wi-Fi EasyConnect [4]	Seconds	Not integrated
ASOP [8]	1.5–2.0 s	Not explicitly measured
ONOS SDN Controller [10]	N/A	~320 ms per rule

187 ms per Rule. This positions our solution as highly competitive, significantly outperforming the onboarding latency of alternative approaches such as the ASOP protocol, which reports onboarding times in the range of 1.5–2.0 seconds, and Wi-Fi EasyConnect, which only provides qualitative timing data on the order of seconds without explicit integration of subsequent policy enforcement.

Regarding policy enforcement, the closest comparable solution is the ONOS SDN Controller, which achieves enforcement latencies of around 320 ms per rule. While the ONOS solution demonstrates a similar enforcement latency, it does not directly incorporate onboarding within its scope. Thus, the advantage of our proposed architecture lies not only in its comparable enforcement speed but also in its seamless integration of secure onboarding with immediate enforcement, providing an end-to-end lifecycle security solution in under one second.

Overall, the comparison underscores the efficacy and efficiency of the proposed architecture, emphasizing its strengths in integrating and automating secure onboarding and rapid policy enforcement within a unified, standards-compliant framework.

5.3 Threat MUD Evaluation and Response

This section details the evaluation of the Threat MUD component, emphasizing the responsiveness and integration capabilities of dynamic threat mitigation within the lifecycle security architecture. Similar to the previous evaluation, the primary aim here is to demonstrate correct operational integration rather than to evaluate the scalability or complexity of the rule enforcement. Therefore, each Threat MUD file tested includes only two straightforward mitigation rules (one inbound and one outbound). This simplification facilitates clear timing measurements and keeps the focus firmly on integration and process automation.

Threat notifications were simulated using controlled HTTP POST requests containing unique threat identifiers. Upon receiving these notifications, the Threat MUD Manager automatically retrieves the corresponding Threat MUD file, validates its authenticity, translates the included mitigation rules into iptables commands, and finally propagates these rules to the enforcement point.

Figure 5.5 provides the execution times for processing each distinct threat notification. Results indicate consistent responsiveness, with measured times ranging from 63 ms to 85 ms and a median response time of 67 ms, reflecting high predictability and reliability in threat response across different scenarios. The mean value across all evaluated threats was approximately 70 ms, reaffirming that the architecture provides a rapid and effective security response that meets real-time operational requirements.

The cumulative latency measured at each step is shown in Figure 5.5, with results obtained from 5 different threats. The full process from threat detection to enforcement was completed in under 100 milliseconds, demonstrating that the proposed system is capable of reacting to emerging threats in near real-time, without requiring manual intervention or static patching logic.

A critical aspect evaluated was the ability to integrate Threat MUD dynamically and seamlessly into the existing MUD infrastructure without requiring manual intervention or significant additional overhead. The Threat MUD Manager was developed to leverage existing

Figure 5.5: Threat MUD Phase Execution Time per Threat

MUD management procedures, allowing straightforward incorporation of new threat-related metadata. The architecture demonstrated an efficient mechanism to automatically handle threat-driven policy updates, highlighting its adaptability to dynamic threat intelligence environments.

The most notable integration challenge at the project’s inception was the lack of a standardized mechanism within the existing FDO or MUD specifications to incorporate threat-specific metadata dynamically. To address this, the Threat MUD extension was designed to operate independently yet remain fully compatible with the standard MUD architecture. This required defining clear interactions and data flows between the Threat MUD Manager, orchestrator, and enforcement points. Ensuring compatibility and seamless transitions between MUD policies and dynamic threat-driven policies constituted a significant design and implementation achievement of this work.

To contextualize the performance of the Threat MUD extension, let’s compare the process latency from the threat received until applied rules against other state-of-the-art dynamic security systems.

Table 5.2 compares enforcement delays of the Threat MUD mechanism developed in this work against other contemporary threat mitigation systems. The results clearly highlight the exceptional responsiveness of the Threat MUD solution, achieving enforcement delays consistently below 100 ms. This low latency in the process is mainly attributed to the fully automated pipeline designed for rapid threat metadata retrieval, validation, translation, and enforcement.

By comparison, the ONOS SDN Controller—commonly considered a high-performance

Table 5.2: Comparison of Enforcement Delays for Threat Mitigation Systems

Solution	Enforcement Delay	Notes / Source
Threat MUD	<100 ms	Fully automated mitigation pipeline, including rule translation
ONOS SDN Controller [10]	~320 ms	Intent insertion latency using flow rules in SDN
AWS IoT Device Defender [11]	>1.5 s <5 s	Uses cloud-based IAM and alert-to-action model via Lambda
Manual Security Response	Minutes–Hours	Human-in-the-loop firewall or DNS rule updates

enforcement solution—exhibits approximately 320 ms of delay, significantly higher than the Threat MUD approach. The AWS IoT Device Defender, leveraging cloud infrastructure and a Lambda-based alert-to-action model, introduces considerably longer delays, typically ranging from 1.5 to 5 seconds. Lastly, traditional manual security responses, which require human intervention for firewall or DNS rule updates, result in latency ranging from several minutes up to hours.

The comparison underscores that the Threat MUD approach developed in this work offers substantial advantages in automated threat response speed and integration simplicity, making it especially suitable for environments requiring immediate reaction to emerging threats.

5.4 End-to-End Lifecycle Security Summary

To evaluate the overall effectiveness of the proposed system, the onboarding, policy enforcement, and threat response stages were executed in sequence, simulating the full lifecycle of an IoT device under active security management. The measurements capture the cumulative latency introduced at each phase and reflect the responsiveness of the system under normal and adverse conditions.

As shown in Figures 5.5 and 5.3, the entire process from secure onboarding using FDO, through MUD-based policy application, to dynamic response with Threat MUD—completes in approximately 800 milliseconds. Each component contributes predictably to the lifecycle, and the design allows for fully autonomous execution once the device is deployed.

The FDO onboarding step accounts for just less than 300 milliseconds, followed by 374 milliseconds for MUD policy retrieval, validation, and enforcement. In the case of a threat, the Threat MUD component can complete detection to enforcement within another 100 milliseconds. Compared to conventional alternatives, which require human intervention, firmware updates, or manual firewall rule changes, the automated lifecycle management presented here is significantly faster and inherently scalable.

Beyond latency metrics, the system achieves a high degree of policy fidelity and compliance with best practices such as zero-touch deployment, least privilege, and threat-informed. These results demonstrate that the integration of FDO, MUD, and Threat MUD provides not

only technical functionality but also a practical and responsive security posture adaptable to dynamic IoT environments.

5.5 Comparison with Alternative Solutions

This section provides an extensive comparative analysis, emphasizing the strengths and positioning of the proposed lifecycle security architecture within the broader context of existing onboarding and enforcement solutions. The results summarized in Table 5.3 and Table 5.2 clearly illustrate that our solution offers distinct advantages in automation, latency, integration completeness, and adherence to modern regulatory frameworks.

When comparing onboarding capabilities, our integrated FDO and MUD architecture achieves an average onboarding latency of approximately 256 ms, significantly faster than alternative solutions such as Wi-Fi EasyConnect, which provides only qualitative assurances without measurable integration into subsequent security policy enforcement. Similarly, the ASOP protocol, while offering advanced post-quantum cryptographic features, still incurs a substantially longer latency (1.5–2.0 seconds). Our system uniquely combines a fast onboarding process with immediate and automatic behavioral policy enforcement through the MUD mechanism, significantly enhancing initial device security from the moment it is activated.

The evaluation of enforcement mechanisms further highlights the competitive advantage of the proposed solution. With policy enforcement averaging 374 ms post-onboarding and dynamic threat-driven enforcement (Threat MUD) consistently below 100 ms, the presented architecture delivers performance comparable to specialized, high-performance solutions like the ONOS SDN Controller. Unlike ONOS, however, our solution offers seamless integration with onboarding processes, enabling a cohesive, automated lifecycle security framework without requiring separate configuration or orchestration phases.

Beyond technical performance, a significant strength of the proposed approach is its compliance and alignment with emerging regulatory requirements, notably the CRA. The CRA mandates strict adherence to secure-by-design and secure-by-default principles, emphasizing automated and auditable security controls throughout device lifecycle phases. Our approach explicitly addresses these regulatory principles through automated cryptographic onboarding (via FDO), transparent behavior constraints (via MUD), and adaptive threat mitigation (via Threat MUD). By automating and embedding these security measures from the initial provisioning, our system substantially reduces the risk of misconfiguration and operational vulnerabilities, effectively meeting CRA standards for device and network security.

The integration challenges and solutions described in earlier sections underscore the comprehensiveness of our approach. The explicit inclusion of the MUD URL within FDO metadata, the automated retrieval and translation of MUD and Threat MUD files, and the seamless enforcement pipeline demonstrate a high degree of operational readiness. These achievements not only streamline the device onboarding and management processes but also significantly enhance overall security posture by minimizing manual intervention and associated human errors.

The presented architecture distinguishes itself by covering the complete lifecycle security spectrum—from initial device onboarding to ongoing policy enforcement and dynamic threat response—while achieving industry-leading latencies and seamless automation. Its full alignment with critical regulatory frameworks, particularly the CRA, positions it not merely as a

competitive technical solution, but also as a practical and robust model ready for real-world deployment in regulated environments.

To conclude the evaluation, Table 5.3 presents a comprehensive comparison between the proposed architecture and several commonly adopted onboarding and security approaches. The table highlights key evaluation criteria, including automation, lifecycle coverage, reaction time to threats, standards compliance, and vendor neutrality.

Table 5.3: Comparison of secure onboarding and lifecycle security solutions

Feature / Solution	This Work	Manual Provisioning	Wi-Fi DPP	AWS IoT Core
Secure Onboarding	✓	✗	✓	✓
Zero-touch Deployment	✓	✗	✓	✓
Automated Policy Enforcement	✓	✗	✗	✓
Dynamic Threat Mitigation	✓	✗	✗	✗
Time from Threat to Enforcement	<300 ms	Minutes	Not supported	Not supported
Standards-based	✓	✗	✓	✗
Vendor Lock-in	✗	✗	✓	✓
Lifecycle Security Coverage	Full	Onboarding only	Onboarding only	Partial
Interoperability	✓	✗	✗	✗

The comparison summarizes a detailed comparative analysis between the proposed architecture and alternative secure onboarding and lifecycle security solutions, specifically Manual Provisioning, Wi-Fi Device Provisioning Protocol (DPP), and AWS IoT Core. Each solution was evaluated against critical criteria such as secure onboarding, zero-touch deployment, automated policy enforcement, dynamic threat mitigation capabilities, time from threat detection to enforcement, adherence to standards, vendor lock-in risks, completeness of lifecycle security coverage, and interoperability.

The analysis demonstrates that the solution developed in this work uniquely fulfills all evaluated features except vendor lock-in, as it intentionally avoids reliance on proprietary mechanisms. In contrast, manual provisioning lacks fundamental capabilities such as secure onboarding, automated enforcement, and rapid threat response, resulting in significant latency (minutes to hours) and increased operational risk due to manual interventions. Wi-Fi DPP, despite supporting standards-based secure onboarding, does not offer automated policy enforcement or dynamic threat mitigation, significantly limiting its applicability to initial provisioning scenarios only. AWS IoT Core provides secure onboarding and partial lifecycle security coverage but lacks dynamic threat mitigation capabilities and introduces vendor lock-in due to its proprietary cloud-centric implementation.

Overall, the proposed architecture stands out clearly by combining comprehensive lifecycle security coverage, standards compliance, rapid automated responses, and robust interoperability. These features collectively position it as a highly effective solution for secure IoT deployments.

6 Conclusion and future directions

This work has addressed critical challenges in the secure onboarding and lifecycle management of IoT devices, proposing a robust, integrated solution based on three complementary technologies: FDO, MUD, and Threat MUD. The primary contribution of this research lies in the successful integration and automation of these components, establishing a unified, automated security pipeline capable of securing devices from the very moment they join the network and throughout their operational lifecycle.

The evaluation results have clearly demonstrated that the proposed system provides significant improvements over traditional manual provisioning methods and state-of-the-art alternatives in terms of automation, performance, and adherence to security standards. Specifically, the combination of FDO and MUD enables rapid onboarding and immediate enforcement of device-specific policies, fully automating the deployment and behavioral constraint process without requiring operator intervention.

A critical aspect of the work was the challenge of integrating the metadata exchange between the FDO protocol and the MUD management infrastructure. The initial design of FDO did not account for behavioral policy metadata such as MUD URLs. Therefore, extending the protocol to support additional device metadata without violating the standard or compromising security proved to be one of the central challenges overcome in this research. The implemented solution, which involved injecting custom metadata into the FDO onboarding flow, represented a practical yet sophisticated adaptation of the standard, validating the flexibility and extensibility of the FDO protocol.

Importantly, the inclusion of the MUD URL in the FDO process—implemented through a simple HTTP POST from the Owner Server to the MUD Manager—was shown to have negligible impact on the overall onboarding latency. As confirmed by experimental results, the average onboarding duration remained around 256 ms, proving that this metadata integration does not compromise performance. This reinforces that secure metadata handoff between FDO and MUD can be achieved efficiently without disrupting the original onboarding design.

The architectural benefits of combining FDO and MUD are further underscored by the comparative analysis shown in Table 5.3. Unlike alternative solutions such as manual provisioning, Wi-Fi DPP, or AWS IoT Core, the proposed system is the only one that offers full coverage of the device lifecycle—from zero-touch onboarding to automated policy enforcement and dynamic threat mitigation. Most notably, it is the only approach capable of enforcing behavior-based rules immediately upon deployment. This level of integration and coverage makes it uniquely positioned to secure devices in real-world environments where manual configuration is impractical or slow to react.

Furthermore, the work prioritized demonstrating the effectiveness and reliability of the integration rather than examining the scalability of the enforcement mechanisms themselves. The choice to test the system with minimal complexity (only two rules per MUD and Threat MUD files) was deliberate, aiming to isolate and validate integration and workflow automation

rather than assess scalability under complex scenarios. While this design decision limited direct insights into large-scale deployments, it was essential to ensure clear, reproducible results that underscore the robust automation achieved. Future work could leverage more complex enforcement scenarios to further validate performance and reliability under realistic, large-scale conditions.

Additionally, the implemented Threat MUD extension significantly enhanced the security lifecycle by enabling automated, rapid responses to new threats. This feature fills a crucial gap in traditional MUD deployments by allowing network policies to adapt dynamically and autonomously to evolving threats, demonstrating the system's capability to maintain high security standards even under changing threat landscapes.

Moreover, the compliance with regulatory frameworks, particularly the European Union's Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) [5], was another significant achievement. By embedding secure-by-design principles, automated secure provisioning, and dynamic security management, the architecture meets key CRA requirements for both preventive and reactive security. As such, the proposed system not only advances technical capabilities but also provides a practical and compliant path for organizations preparing for upcoming IoT cybersecurity regulations.

6.1 Future direction

While the current implementation validates the core architectural principles and demonstrates strong performance, several avenues for future enhancement remain open. Firstly, the rule enforcement mechanism in both MUD and Threat MUD is currently limited to basic ACLs at the network layer. To support richer security semantics and more expressive policies, future work should explore the integration of a Medium-level Security Policy Language (MSPL) [12]. MSPL allows for the formal specification of multi-dimensional security policies that go beyond simple allow/deny lists, enabling behavior adaptation based on context, threat level, or user roles. Secondly, while the current testbed confirms the system's viability under controlled conditions, further validation is needed in more complex environments. Deploying the solution in real Software-Defined Networking (SDN) infrastructures or industrial control settings would help evaluate scalability, resilience, and real-world interoperability. In particular, SDN integration could enable dynamic flow-based enforcement and multi-tenant policy coordination, further enhancing the architecture's flexibility and impact. Finally, to support broader adoption and compliance, future versions should aim to implement standardized mechanisms for Threat MUD file generation, verification, and distribution. This would ensure trustworthiness across federated environments and prevent misconfigurations or policy conflicts. The adoption of structured threat intelligence formats such as STIX, and integration with established CTI platforms like MISP, would also be beneficial. In conclusion, this work establishes a solid foundation for end-to-end IoT lifecycle security, and opens the path for further research into adaptive, scalable, and standards-compliant protection mechanisms for the growing landscape of connected devices.

Bibliography

- [1] Geoffrey Cooper, Brad Behm, Ankur Chakraborty, Hanu Kommalapati, Giri Mandyam, Hannes Tschofenig, and Witali Bartsch. Fido device onboard specification 1.1, 2022. URL <https://fidoalliance.org/specs/FIDO/FIDO-Device-Onboard-PS-v1.1-20220419>.
- [2] Dylan Dodson, Tanya Brewer, Ron Ross, Jon Boyens, Murugiah Souppaya, Karen Scarfone, and Angela Smith. Securing small-business and home iot devices: Mitigating network-based attacks using manufacturer usage description (mud). Special Publication 1800-15, National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), 2021. URL <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.1800-15>.
- [3] Eliot Lear, Ralph Droms, and Dan Romascanu. Manufacturer usage description specification, March 2019. URL <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc8520>.
- [4] WI-FI ALLIANCE. Wi-fi easy connect specification, 2022. URL https://www.wi-fi.org/system/files/Wi-Fi_Easy_Connect_Specification_v3.0.pdf.
- [5] Eu cyber resilience act. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/2847/oj>, 2024. Accessed May 2025.
- [6] FIDO Alliance. Fido device onboard implementation, 2023. URL <https://github.com/fido-device-onboard/pri-fidoiot>.
- [7] Silia Maksuti, Ani Bicaku, Mario Zsilak, Igor Ivkić, Bálint Péceli, Gábor Singler, Kristóf Kovács, Markus Tauber, and Jerker Delsing. Automated and secure onboarding for system of systems. *IEEE Access*, 9:111095–111108, 2021. doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3102280.
- [8] Khan Reaz and Gerhard Wunder. Asop: A sovereign and secure device onboarding protocol for cloud-based iot services. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.13020*, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2403.13020>.
- [9] Marcin Witczak, Lothar Seybold, Eric Bulach, and Niko Maucher. *Modern IoT Onboarding Platforms for Advanced Applications: A Practitioner's Guide to KIS.ME*. Springer Nature, 2023. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-33623-2.
- [10] Usman M. Rathore M. A. Risdianto, A. C. Transforming network management: Intent-based flexible control empowered by efficient flow-centric visibility, 2024. URL <https://doi.org/10.3390/fi16070223>.
- [11] Aws iot device defender documentation. <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/iot/latest/developerguide/device-defender.html>, 2024. Accessed May 2025.

- [12] Alejandro Molina Zarca, Jorge Bernal Bernabe, Ruben Trapero, Diego Rivera, Jesus Villalobos, Antonio Skarmeta, Stefano Bianchi, Anastasios Zafeiropoulos, and Panagiotis Gouvas. Security management architecture for nfv/sdn-aware iot systems. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 6(5):8005–8020, 2019. doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2019.2904123.
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